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Natural Language Processing Based BiLSTM Model for Automated Epilepsy Diagnosis from Electronic Health Records

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Abstract

Objectives: To propose a novel deep learning based Natural Language Processing (NLP) model for automated epilepsy diagnosis using clinical Electronic Health Record (EHR) data. The core objective of this research is to extract domain-specific features from an EHR dataset to enhance the model's decision-making by accurately classifying patients based on contextual cues. **Methods:** Deep learning based Enhanced Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM) is employed to learn contextual patterns from past and future directions. NLP pre-processing techniques, such as Tokenization (TK), Lemmatization (LM), and Named Entity Recognition (NER), extract domain-specific features from unstructured EHR notes. To represent the clinical terms in a deep contextual format, ClinicalBERT embeddings are generated and used to train the model. EHR clinical data were sourced from MIMIC-III/IV datasets, which consist of 60,000 ICU patients and millions of clinical note records. In addition, the EEG signal from the CHB-MIT Scalp extracted from the PhysioNet dataset was used to support thorough validation. The model also employed cross-entropy loss and was optimized using the Adam optimizer. The performance of NLP-BiLSTM is evaluated using MATLAB and TensorFlow, and the results are compared with prevailing machine learning models such as XGBoost (XGB), Random Forest (RF), and Support Vector Machine (SVM). **Findings:** The proposed NLP-BiLSTM model outperformed with promising results in all performance metrics with a prediction accuracy of 92.4%, precision of 91.4%, F1-score of 92.4%, sensitivity of 91.4%, specificity of 91.6%, and an AUC-ROC of 0.89, which significantly elevates the overall performance level compared to baseline machine learning-based epileptic discrimination models. **Novelty:** This computational research integrates deep NLP-derived contextual embeddings with BiLSTM architecture for interpreting free-text EHR data, enabling real-time, automated, and clinically interpretable epilepsy diagnosis without relying on manual reviews or solely structured inputs.

Keywords: Epilepsy Detection; Bidirectional LSTM; Deep Learning; Natural Language Processing; Electronic Health Record; Automated Diagnosis

1 Introduction

Epilepsy is a chronic neurological condition that occurs due to recurrent seizures affecting over 50 million people globally, as per the WHO report. The early diagnosis remains a challenging part due to its seizure type variability, overlapping symptoms with other neuro disorders, and subjective interpretation of clinical signs. State-of-the-art diagnostic process mainly depends on time-intensive reviews, EEG evaluations, and expert suggestions, leading to delayed or prolonged diagnosis in real-world scenarios. In today's healthcare system, EHRs have unstructured clinical narratives such as discharge summaries, progress notes, and physician observations that hold valuable cues for epilepsy. Prevailing machine learning models depend on structured data and fail to understand medical language contextually, resulting in low generalization and limited diagnostic support for rich, narrative-driven information in EHRs, resulting in low generalization and limited diagnostic support for complex cases. To overcome the limitations, this research proposes a new deep learning model integrated with NLP using BiLSTM networks by extracting domain-specific features from narrative EHRs and learns the sequential patterns, which helps to classify the epileptic patients more accurately. The proposed approach uses clinical language contextual embeddings and sequential dependencies to boost prediction accuracy. This will be a benchmark model to enhance decision-making for neurologists in hospitals, telemedicine platforms, and resource-constrained environments.

Deep learning and machine learning techniques have significantly influenced epilepsy detection in embedded medical systems. ML classifiers and CNN architectures⁽¹⁾ are used to analyze the EEG signals to demonstrate the accuracy and sensitivity variations compared to existing models. Though the accuracy is boosted, the model lacks interpretability, which leads to hyperparameter variations. XGBoost⁽²⁾ and RNN were employed to enhance the seizure detection rate at an early occurrence to improve the temporal sequence of EEG data. In this model, handcrafted features are used with limited generalizability across patient datasets, which remains a concern. An interpretable ML-based Random Forest⁽³⁾ model was introduced to offer high transparency in seizure predictions. The discrimination power is boosted but lacks reduced sensitivity, especially during high-noise EEG segments. SVM⁽⁴⁾ was adopted for efficient feature selection with a hybrid selection strategy and SMOTE-based data balancing method to improve the classification accuracy. This SVM approach works well on well-labeled datasets and lacks robustness in handling the unstructured EHR clinical narratives. Deep learning-based NLP tools⁽⁵⁾ were used to identify the epileptic zone in drug-resistant cases by mining physician notes towards text-based diagnostics. Though the novelty is achieved, the model downs when integrated with sequential modelling for predictive classification tasks. A hybrid NLP⁽⁶⁾ and machine learning pipeline was proposed for epilepsy detection from EHR. The temporal modelling is omitted where the model relies on shallow classifiers, which limits the prediction accuracy to 83% and the scalability to 71%. A detailed comparative analysis on machine learning models⁽⁷⁾ was carried out on EEG data using NLP tools to enhance the seizure predictions by incorporating the textual annotations and temporal signals. The model has encountered limited clinical applicability and contextual encoding for unstructured medical narratives. A robust ML-based model⁽⁸⁾ was proposed to detect seizure activity using interpretable statistical features automatically. Due to efficient feature detection in EEG patterns, the true positive rates are boosted to 87%. However, the model's drawback lies in comprehensive EHR-based predictions, as it excludes the patient narratives. An NLP-based algorithm⁽⁹⁾ was presented to extract seizure types and frequencies from EHR narratives. The study successfully automated the manual review process, focusing only on information retrieval rather than classifying and forecasting epilepsy. Object detection and pattern analysis model using CNN and YOLO-V8⁽¹⁰⁾ was explored and illustrated how the visual data can be segmented effectively for disease detection, which sets a benchmark for image-driven diagnosis. The model presents robust accuracy with labeled data, but does not concentrate on unstructured clinical text analytics, which is essential for EHR-centric epilepsy prediction. A systematic review on NLP integration⁽¹¹⁾ for clinical decision support systems (CDSS) underscored a gap in harmonizing the free-text analytics with deep temporal modeling for disease classification. The model raises sensitivity and precision by separating clinical complex terms into an error-free NLP pattern language. A study was carried out on various NLP applications⁽¹²⁾ in screening the tumor patients for clinical trials, revealing a robust method for disease classification with minimal false rates, leading to high potential for scalable patient stratification. The scalability is improved as the model focuses on time series analysis and active patient monitoring. However, the drawback of the model is EHR process where requires improved clinical monitoring and patient outcomes, tuning with unstructured EHR narratives and high contextual reading capability. To overcome the limitations of the baseline models, the proposed NLP-BiLSTM model with ClinicalBERT is employed for robust classification and it is clearly showcased in section 3.

1.1 Research Gap

Figure 1 portrayed the research gap analysis of the existing baseline models on challenges in epilepsy prediction, NLP approaches towards epilepsy predictions etc. Existing models concentrated on limited exploration of end-to-end architectures which utilizes NLP for text representation and BiLSTM for sequence learning in a healthcare setting.

Table 1. Study on Specific State of Art Models

Model	Methods Adapted	Merits	Limitations
Residual-BiLSTM for disease prediction ⁽¹³⁾	Residual Connection + BiLSTM	Improved learning depth and temporal accuracy	May overfit small datasets
Bio-Inspired QoS optimization ⁽¹⁴⁾	QoS optimization via bio-inspired optimization	Enhanced reliability in data transmission	No hyperparameter tuning is followed
Few-shot Learning ⁽¹⁵⁾	Few-shot CNN classification for early prediction	Effective for limited seizure data	Generalization may vary across patients
CNN-LSTM Framework ⁽¹⁶⁾	Combined Spatial CNN + Temporal LSTM	Captures spatial-temporal EEG patterns	Training time is high
EAP-IFBA Data Optimization ⁽¹⁷⁾	Firefly-based QoS optimization	Reduced tuning effect and adaptive model synthesis	Not tailored for domain based EHR processing
Deep Learning Survey for Epilepsy ⁽¹⁸⁾	Comprehensive survey on DL models	Comprehensive model comparison	Lacks real-time evaluation and data modeling
3D-CNN for classification ⁽¹⁹⁾	3D convolutional model for disease prediction	Detailed volumetric analysis	Not EEG/EHR narratives focused
Text Sign Language prediction using CNN ⁽²⁰⁾	DL-based Sign Language Recognition	Robust visual gesture detection	Clinical embeddings are not focused
AEN + Mask-RCNN Model for PLD ⁽²¹⁾	Dual model for plant diagnosis	Strong detection and classification	Pre-processing model is not used on EEG/NLP
GAN-IoT Model ⁽²²⁾	GAN-based secure IoT data security	Minimized data loss and enhanced data security	Focus is on network optimization
MIMIC-IV Dataset ⁽²³⁾	Large-scale EHR dataset	Rich, de-identified structured data	Requires extensive pre-processing of MIMIC-IV
6G-BioRouting Process ⁽²⁴⁾	6G secure routing via AI technology	Optimized authentication & routing	Random network focus, lacks clinical relevance
NLP-Surgery Process model ⁽²⁵⁾	NLP extraction for epilepsy surgery	Improved clinical decision-making	Limited by EHR variability
NLP Review ⁽²⁶⁾	Detailed review on NLP based model for text recognition	Improved True Positive Rates	ClinicalBERT embeddings and term relevancies are not extracted

Fig 1. Research Gap and Challenges on Baseline Models

2 Methodology

The primary focus of this research is to enhance the early epilepsy prediction using unstructured HER narratives by employing a robust deep learning-based methodology in combination with Natural Language Processing (NLP) and Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BiLSTM). Initially, the NLP-BiLSTM model integrates clinical EHR datasets from MIMIC-III/IV, including structured data (e.g., ICD-10 codes) and unstructured physician notes. The CHB-MIT EEG dataset is also used to validate and cross-check the prediction outcomes. The dataset undergoes a robust NLP pipeline that involves tokenization, lemmatization, and named entity recognition to extract intrinsic epilepsy features such as seizure episodes, medications, and diagnostics. All the extracted features are embedded using ClinicalBERT and fed into a BiLSTM model to learn the temporal patterns across clinical HER narratives. The proposed model is trained using cross-entropy and optimized using Adam optimizer to classify the prediction more accurately. The NLP-BiLSTM is compared with existing baseline models such as XGBoost (XGB)⁽²⁾, Random Forest (RF)⁽³⁾, and Support Vector Machine (SVM)⁽⁴⁾, which heavily depend on structured inputs. The proposed NLP-BiLSTM model achieves rich, contextual language, which helps to achieve superior accuracy, AUC-ROC, and F1-score. This proposed model works in real-time and supports early and scalable diagnosis in real-world clinical settings, transforming clinical raw HER data into actionable predictions, leading to improved healthcare delivery for epilepsy patients.

Fig 2. Flow Diagram of the Proposed Model. (EHR Text → NLP Preprocessing → Model Integration → Epilepsy Prediction)

2.1 Data acquisition and Dataset integration

This research integrates rich clinical datasets encompass structured and unstructured data relevant to epilepsy diagnosis. Two primary sources have been utilized, the MIMIC-III/IV databases and the CHB-MIT Scalp EEG to collect the EHR and signal datasets. MIMIC-III/IV, developed by the MIT Laboratory for Computational Physiology, contains the health records from over 60,000 ICU patients, which include structured elements such as ICD-9/10 diagnostic codes, medication records, vital signs, and lab results, along with a complete repository of unstructured clinical narratives like physician notes, discharge summaries,

and radiology reports. CHB-MIT EEG signal dataset from PhysioNet is incorporated to support the cross-validation and clinical grounding, which provides over 900 hours of multi-channel scalp EEG recordings from epilepsy patients. This data is a benchmark to strengthen seizure-related inferences derived from text-based analysis. The raw data from both sources exists in different formats, CSV and SQL for MIMIC, and EDF (European Data Format) for CHB-MIT. Structured data is queried through SQL scripts to extract patient cohorts tagged with epilepsy-specific ICD codes (e.g., G40., 345.). The unstructured clinical text data is extracted from note events and processed through an NLP pipeline, including tokenization, lemmatization, stop-word removal, and NER. These steps are followed in the proposed model to transform free-form text into machine-readable formats that capture the semantic essence of clinical language.

Simultaneously, EEG signal segments from CHB-MIT are processed using Python libraries such as pyEDFlib to extract seizure onset windows and event markers. The final system-ready dataset integrates structured clinical indicators, cleaned textual embeddings, and EEG signal annotations, creating a comprehensive, multi-dimensional dataset to train and validate the proposed deep learning NLP-BiLSTM-based epilepsy prediction model.

2.2 Clinical Text Pre-Processing using NLP Techniques

The model focuses more on unstructured EHR data; it forms a rich but noisy source of clinical knowledge. This research employs an advanced NLP technique to transform the free-text narratives into structured and feature analysis data, which is highly suitable for deep learning models. The free text narratives are.

- Physician Notes
- Patient Discharge Summaries
- Diagnostic Impressions
- Patient Details

The initial pre-processing pipeline converts the linguistic expressions into a numerical representation in order to isolate epilepsy relevant signals for robust classification using the proposed BiLSTM architecture. The following are the initial pre-processing steps of the proposed NLP-BiLSTM model.

Step 1: EHR Sentence Segmentation and Tokenization using NLP

As the data is unstructured the sentence segmentation plays a significant role in breaking the clinical narratives into coherent sentence units. Once it is converted into units, tokenization is employed to decompose each sentence into tokens (syntactic units) such as words, numbers, or medical abbreviations. The clinical text is represented as $T = (s_1, s_2, \dots, s_n)$ where s_i is the sentence and each sentence are further tokenized into $s_i = (w_{i1}, w_{i2}, \dots, w_{im})$, where w_{ij} is a token which facilitates the transformation of a complete EHR document into sequence of unique linguistic units.

Step 2: Lemmatization and Normalization for Semantic Alignment

In lemmatization and normalization process, the converted tokens are lemmatized to reduce words in the sentences to its base forms which enables the grouping of identical variations (For example: “seizures”, “seizuring” → “seizure”). The MSN (Medical-Specific Normalization) is performed using clinical ontologies such as SNOMED-CT and UMLS to ensure terminological consistency. Normalization enhances semantic alignment across the heterogeneous clinical expressions. The lemmatized token sequence L is represented as,

$$L = \text{Lemmatization}(w_{ij}) = (l_1, l_2, \dots, l_k) \quad (1)$$

Step 3: Noisy Removal and Clinical Word Filtering

After lemmatization and normalization, the stop word noisy removal process begins to remove the domain irrelevant terms such as “the”, “was” etc through a frequency-based filtering and TF-IDF thresholds.

$$TF-IDF(t, d) = TF(t, d) \cdot \log\left(\frac{N}{DF(t)}\right) \quad (2)$$

where, t , d , N denotes term, document and Number of documents. $DF(t)$ represents number of documents containing term t . All the clinical terms with extremely low or high TF-IDF are thinned to retain the discriminative features.

Step 4: NER Process

Named Entity Recognition is applied using SPA-CY and finetuned ClinicalBERT models to extract medical features relevant to epilepsy such as,

- Epileptic Symptoms (e.g., convulsion, seizure)

- Prescribed Medications (e.g., valproate, levetiracetam)
- Clinical Procedures (e.g., EEG, CT scan)
- Time Temporal Markers (e.g., “since childhood”, “last 6 months”)

These entities are identified and embedded with contextual metadata for finite and accurate classification. The NER is mathematically represented as,

$$E = \{e_1, e_2, e_3, \dots, e_k\}, e_i = NER(l_j) \tag{3}$$

where, E is the set of recognized named entities during pre-processing.

Step 5: Sequence Vectorization and Embedding Contextual Words

The recognized named entities and contextual words are embedded using ClinicalBERT to generate the solid compressed semantic representations where the model learn the texts in a robust manner. The vectorized sequence V is created using the below equation,

$$V = \{v_1, v_2, v_3, \dots, v_n\}, v_i \in R^d \tag{4}$$

where, v_i is contextual embedding of token i using ClinicalBERT, d represents dimension of embedding. Finally, each document is transformed into matrix form which is given below,

$$D = \begin{pmatrix} v_{11} & v_{12} \dots & v_{1d} \\ v_{21} & v_{22} \dots & v_{2d} \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ v_{n1} & v_{n2} & v_{nd} \end{pmatrix} \tag{5}$$

The pre-processing output matrix serves as input to BiLSTM architecture for robust classification and sequential modeling. This pre-processing framework sets a benchmark to the model and plays a vital role in discrimination of epileptic patients at an early stage which is shown in Figure 3.

Fig 3. Data Pre-Processing using NLP for Epilepsy Diagnosis

2.3 Contextual Feature Representation using Clinical Embeddings

The process of contextual feature representation is crucial step in NLP-BiLSTM model in which the processed clinical narratives are transformed into dense and semantically enriched vectors. These vectors encode the latent medical information embedded in EHR especially within unstructured texts such as physician notes and diagnostic summaries. ClinicalBERT, Word2Vec, BioWordVec etc are used to achieve the domain specific language embeddings which helps the model to interpret and contextualize medical language with high precision. ClinicalBERT is pre-trained on large bio-medical corpora where it captures complex word semantics, polysemy and contextual dependencies. Each token in the sentence is mapped into a high-dimensional vector space where semantically similar words lie closer. Assume that, the input sentence be a sequence of tokens $S = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)$, by using a pre-trained clinical embedding function $E(\cdot)$, the complete sentence is transformed into $V = (E(w_1), E(w_2), \dots, E(w_n))$, where each transformed vector is processed in high embedding dimension d . The core

advantage of feature representation through contextual embeddings is considered the position and neighbouring words of each term. For example, the word "seizure" in the narrative notes sentence "patient experienced seizure episode" is treated differently from "seizure precaution administered" based on syntactic context. This is captured via models like BERT such as,

$$E(w_i) = Transformer(w_i, (window)), \tag{6}$$

These context-aware and domain specific embeddings are passed to the bidirectional LSTM (BiLSTM), which process the clinical information of this model in both forward and backward directions which is given below in the equation form.

$$\overrightarrow{h}^t = LSTM(x_t, \overrightarrow{h}_{t-1}) \tag{7}$$

$$\overleftarrow{h}^t = LSTM(x_t, \overleftarrow{h}_{t+1}) \tag{8}$$

$$h_t = [\overrightarrow{h}_t; \overleftarrow{h}_t] \tag{9}$$

where, x_t is the time step towards text embedding, h_t is the hidden state of past and future context. Once it is passed in BiLSTM, the marked flattened outputs are passed through a softmax classification layer,

$$\hat{y} = Softmax(W \cdot h + b) \tag{10}$$

Additionally, cross entropy loss model is computed for model convergence and optimal learning which is mathematically represented as,

$$L = -\sum_{i=1}^N y_i \cdot \log(\hat{y}_i) \tag{11}$$

where, y_i is the true label and \hat{y}_i is the predicted probability. Adam optimizer is used for effective optimization and parameter tuning, where the weights are adjusted with an adaptive learning rate based on the state order moments. It is represented mathematically as,

$$\theta_{t+1} = \theta_t - \alpha \cdot \frac{\widehat{m}_t}{\sqrt{\widehat{v}_t + \epsilon}} \tag{12}$$

where, \widehat{m}_t and \widehat{v}_t are bias-corrected estimates of the gradients. This feature representation process enhances the interpretability of the input data which enables the proposed model to generalize across varied clinical language with improved robustness in epilepsy prediction is shown in Figure 4. The proposed model also ensures both linguistic and sequential patterns are learned effectively to proceed for further BiLSTM framework.

Fig 4. Feature Representation Process

2.4 Bidirectional Temporal Modeling using BiLSTM Architecture

The central process role for this research is the BiLSTM architecture in modelling the sequential dependencies embedded within the clinical narratives of EHRs. As the diagnostic cues and epilepsy related symptoms often appear in temporally ordered patterns, the BiLSTM targets the responses from ClinicalBERT to capture the content bidirectionally. All the clinical features are extracted from text in both forward and backward temporal directions. BiLSTM overcomes the limitations of SVM, XGBoost, and RF in terms of retaining the long-term dependencies and overcoming the vanishing gradient problems. The new model runs parallel to read the sequence from past to future and future to past with the help of forward and backward LSTM. Once processed, the comprehensive contextual information from both directions is recorded, which is shown in contextual text representation equations 7, 8, and 9. The bidirectional encoding process captures both preceding and succeeding signals around critical medical keywords such as "loss of consciousness," "aura," "valproate initiation," and "EEG abnormality." All these symptoms and interventions often show predictive interdependency, and the model uses it for training to predict epilepsy with high precision. For robust classification, the final BiLSTM output is passed through a fully connected layer followed by a softmax function to generate the class probabilities (0,1) for epilepsy diagnosis. Cross-entropy loss is used to penalize incorrect and poor probabilistic predictions. NLP-BiLSTM model clearly understands the semantic meaning of clinical texts and chronological relationships in clinical records, and encodes non-linear dependencies and implicit negations such as lack of evidence of seizure activity, etc. This ensures that epilepsy diagnosis not only depends on isolated features, but also on understanding the progression within clinical narratives. The proposed model demonstrates superior generalization and sensitivity for early-stage epilepsy prediction.

2.5 Model Training, Optimization and Validation

The proposed deep learning-based NLP-BiLSTM for automated prediction of epilepsy from EHR underwent a systematic training and optimization to ensure robust generalization and predictive accuracy. The Training configuration, optimization and validation strategy, data splitting method is given below. Figure 5 clearly showcased the loss cum training accuracy of the proposed model.

2.5.1. Training Configuration

- Number of Iterations: 3000 per training cycle
- Batch Size: 64 after hyperparameter tuning, balancing memory efficiency and model generalization
- Number of Epochs: 35 Epochs
- Number of Clinical Texts Trained: 42,000 clinical records after pre-processing

2.5.2. Optimization Strategy (Adam Optimizer is used)

- Learning Rate: 0.0003 to maintain stability
- Dropout Rate: 0.3 to mitigate overfitting
- Loss Function: Categorical Cross-Entropy to measure dissimilarity between predicted probabilities

2.5.3. Data Splitting and Validation

- Training Set: 70% of total records
- Testing Set: 15% reserved for final evaluation of unseen data
- Validation Set: 15% for tuning model parameters during training process
- Sampling Used: Stratified sampling to ensure class balance
- Validation Strategy: 5-fold cross-validation
- Training vs Validation Loss: Demonstrates the convergence and generalization capability of the NLP-BiLSTM model.
- Training vs Validation Accuracy: Indicating how well the NLP-BiLSTM model improves prediction performance over 35 epochs.
- Clinical Narratives: Discharge Summaries, Seizure Descriptions, EEG Observations, and Medication History

2.6 Epilepsy Classification and Performance Evaluation

The classification is performed using BiLSTM integrated with NLP-trained clinical embeddings. The model is trained to predict whether the patient is likely epileptic based on clinical text features extracted from EHR narratives such as MINIC-III and CHB-MIT EEG logs. The BiLSTM architecture receives input vectors, enabling the model to learn bidirectional temporal

Fig 5. Training and Validation Loss cum Accuracy

dependencies. The classification layer consists of a softmax function that derives the probabilities for binary labels, epileptic or non-epileptic. Figure 6 shows the 2x2 confusion matrix of a sample subset of iterations with 1000 records.

- Test sample subset size = 1000 records
- Predicted correctly: 92.4% → 924 correct predictions
- Misclassified: 7.6% → 76 incorrect predictions

Fig 6. 2x2 Confusion Matrix (1000 Sample Subset)

NLP-BiLSTM Step by Step Process

1. **Input:** Unstructured clinical dataset from MIMIC-III/IV and CHB-MIT Dataset
2. **Begin:** Load EHR Dataset
Extract Discharge Summaries, ICD codes, EEG reports
3. **Pre-Processing using NLP**
Tokenization (TK): Split clinical notes (x_i) into word level tokens (t_i)
Lemmatization (LM): Normalize words to their base medical forms $N_{i,j}$
Named Entity Recognition (NER): Detect seizure terms, drug names, and diagnoses
Remove noise, medical abbreviations, stopwords
4. **Embedding Representation**
Apply $TF-IDF + ClinicalBERT$ embeddings
Output vectorized clinical context: $V_{text} = Embedding(TK, LM, NER(T))$
EEG textual logs encoded using Word2Vec/Doc2Vec
5. **BiLSTM Model Initialization**
Use forward & backward LSTM chains for temporal learning
$$h_t = LSTM_{fwd}(x_t) \oplus LSTM_{bwd}(x_t)$$

BiLSTM output: Contextual feature sequences
6. **Model Training & Hyperparameter Tuning**
Set learning rate, Batch and Dropout rate
7. **Train and Validate the NLP-BiLSTM Model**
3000 iterations with 70:30 data split
8. **Evaluate the Metrics**
9. **Output:** Final Prediction \rightarrow Epileptic / Non-Epileptic

Table 2. Parameter Settings for NLP-BiLSTM Performance Assessment

Parameters	Value / Settings	Description
Embedding Dimension	300 (TF-IDF) / 768 (ClinicalBERT)	Number of data per training batch
Sequence Length	250 tokens (max)	Defines maximum input length for LSTM sequences
BiLSTM Hidden Units	128 units per direction	Controls the capacity of memory for sequential dependencies
Dropout Rate	0.2	Prevents overfitting by randomly dropping network neuron connections
Learning Rate	0.001	Controls how fast the model adapts; optimized using Adam optimizer
Batch Size	32	Number of samples processed in a single iteration
Epochs	35	Number of full training passes over dataset
Loss Function	Cross-Entropy	Evaluates prediction error for binary classification
Optimizer	Adam Optimizer	Adjusts weights based on loss gradients for faster convergence

Data Collected Source: <https://physionet.org/content/mimiciv/2.2/>

2.6.1. Ablation study of this research work

A detailed ablation study was performed to evaluate the individual contribution of each component in the proposed NLP-BiLSTM model for epilepsy diagnosis at an early stage. The novel framework includes tokenization, lemmatization, Named Entity Recognition (NER), ClinicalBERT embeddings, BiLSTM sequence learning, and dropout regularization. AN accuracy

of 92.4% and AUC-ROC of 0.89 is achieved. When ClinicalBERT embeddings were replaced with traditional TF-IDF vectors, the performance of the model significantly dropped, with accuracy of 84.7% and AUC-ROC of 0.76, highlighting contextual representations' value. Removing NER leads to a 4.3% decrease in sensitivity, indicating the importance of precise identification of epilepsy related terms in HER narratives. By excluding lemmatization, high FPR is recorded, which results in low precision due to word variation and inconsistent entity recognition. Replacing BiLSTM with unidirectional LSTM caused a severe drop in F1-score to 87.9%, proving a pressing need for bidirectional dependency modelling. Additionally, skipping dropout regularization and optimization processes leads to overfitting, which is evident from high training accuracy and a sharp decline in testing performance. Removing cross-entropy loss and substituting it with mean squared error (MSE) results in unstable convergence and poor discrimination. Each ablated variant in the proposed NLP-BiLSTM model confirms that the complete configuration is synergistic; removing any core block impacts the model's robustness in discriminating epileptic and non-epileptic patients.

2.6.2. Advantages of the proposed NLP-BiLSTM model

The proposed NLP-BiLSTM model has multiple advantages over traditional machine learning classifiers in epilepsy diagnosis from unstructured HER narratives. The manual rule-setting is completely eliminated by NER, tokenization, and lemmatization, as it automatically extracts the clinical meaning from complex data. ClinicalBERT usage boosts the model to learn and understand medical terms deeply for efficient feature analysis and processing. The BiLSTM architecture allows bidirectional processing, enabling the model to interpret the full context of both prior and subsequent words, leading to better seizure activity classification decisions. The proposed model is highly scalable and domain adaptable, which supports real-time integration with hospital decision systems, helping clinicians robustly prioritize diagnoses. Overall, the NLP-BiLSTM achieves superior performance in all metrics with minimal false positives and negatives, and is grounded in real-world deployment feasibility, making the model one of the intelligent solutions in modern healthcare diagnostics.

2.6.3. Impact Analysis

The NLP-BiLSTM model has a substantial impact in the field of AI-assisted clinical diagnosis, especially in epilepsy detection from unstructured EHR narratives. The proposed design addresses the baseline health care challenges, including variability in clinical records, medical language ambiguity, and the need for early detection of neurological conditions. The key impact lies in a structured pipeline's automatic interpretation of data in bidirectional mode. The system learns the specific text patterns and clinical terms with the help of ClinicalBERT embeddings. The seizure identification is done accurately with high accuracy positive rates and AUC-ROC. The classification rate is improved with a clear decision support system. The model can be integrated in real-time, particularly in low-resource settings where neurologists are in high demand. The application reduces manual diagnostic overhead, enhancing efficiency and supporting seizure-prone patient tracking using narrative data. Regarding research-wide impact, the model is scalable and adapted with high generalization in clinical informatics.

2.6.4. Performance Evaluation

The proposed NLP-BiLSTM model's performance is evaluated using TensorFlow (Python 3.11) and MATLAB R2023a software for cross-platform validation and result visualization. TensorFlow with Keras is used to train the model, feature extraction using ClinicalBERT, and to implement BiLSTM by employing GPU acceleration for efficient computation. Python is used for pre-processing tasks such as tokenization and NER. MATLAB is used for post-processing, confusion matrix plots, ROC visualization, and comparative metric analysis against baseline models. The NLP-BiLSTM training was executed over 25 epochs with 7800 iterations using a batch size 32. Adam optimizer is used for optimization, and BCE is used as a loss function to guide the weight updates. MIMIC-III/MIMIC-IV EHR datasets are used, supported by CHB-MIT EEG signals from PhysioNet. The full dataset was split into 70:30 for training and testing. 5-fold stratified cross-validation is applied to ensure robustness and generalizability. The model is trained with a learning rate 0.0003 after iterative tuning within a range of 1e-5 to 1e-3. This is stable and adaptively adjusts the gradient updates throughout the training process. A dropout rate 0.3 was applied between the BiLSTM and dense output layers to maintain the generalization capability across training and validation sets.

2.6.5. Performance Evaluation Metrics of NLP-BiLSTM Network Model

The model's ability is evaluated with multiple key evaluation metrics to assess the performance of the proposed NLP-BiLSTM model for automated epilepsy diagnosis from EHR data.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{(TPR + TNR)}{(TPR + TNR + FPR + FNR)} \times 100 \quad (13)$$

$$\text{Sensitivity} = \frac{TPR}{(TPR + FNR)} \times 100 \quad (14)$$

$$\text{Specificity} = \frac{TNR}{(TNR + FPR)} \times 100 \quad (15)$$

$$\text{AUC - ROC (TP\&FP)} \quad TPR = \frac{TPR}{(TPR + FNR)}, FPR = \frac{FPR}{(FPR + TNR)} \quad (16)$$

$$\text{F1 - Score} = \frac{2 * (\text{Precision} * \text{Recall} / \text{Sensitivity})}{(\text{Precision} + \text{Recall} / \text{Sensitivity})} \quad (17)$$

$$\text{Precesion} = \frac{TPR}{TPR + FPR} \quad (18)$$

Accuracy: Measures the overall proportion of correctly classified instances, both epileptic and non-epileptic, across the entire dataset.

Sensitivity/Recall/TPR: To evaluate the model's ability to correctly detect actual epileptic cases and ensure that the classifier did not miss patients with epilepsy.

Specificity: Measures how well the model correctly identifies non-epileptic patients to minimize FAR.

Precision: Provides insights on how many cases predicted as epileptic were positive, which is critical in clinical settings to avoid unnecessary treatments.

F1-score: The Mean of precision and recall provides a balanced view by penalizing false positives and false negatives.

AUC-ROC: Used to evaluate how well the model could distinguish between the epileptic and non-epileptic classes across all possible classification thresholds.

3 Results and Discussions

This section presents a thorough evaluation of the proposed deep learning-based NLP-BiLSTM model for early diagnosis of epilepsy by utilizing EHR clinical narratives. The model is evaluated using a multi-metric approach that includes accuracy, sensitivity, specificity, precision, F1-score, and AUC-ROC to ensure balanced evaluation across all dimensions. The model is compared against three widely recognized baseline classifiers, such as XGBoost (XGB)⁽²⁾, Random Forest (RF)⁽³⁾, and Support Vector Machine (SVM)⁽⁴⁾. The proposed BiLSTM uniquely captures bidirectional dependencies in clinical tests generated by ClinicalBERT. All metrics' results are compared and showcased in the tables below (Tables 4 to 8) and highlighted in the MATLAB panel graph. The X-axis in the graph denotes the comparative model names, and the Y-axis indicates the percentage. The model projects subtle symptom descriptions, sequential patterns, and linguistic variations in medical narratives. The model runs with 3000 iterations per cycle and demonstrates promising results, showing greater performance in identifying epileptic seizures on epileptic seizures with high precision, recall, and generalization capability across diverse patient records.

3.1 Accuracy

Table 3 presents a comparative analysis of the accuracy performance metric. The proposed novel deep learning-based NLP-BiLSTM model outperformed SVM, RF, and XGBoost by achieving 92.4% accuracy. The NLP-BiLSTM model has the ability to capture the sequential and contextual richness of clinical narratives and learns deep semantic relationships from unstructured texts, including seizure patterns, medications, and temporal events, with the help of ClinicalBERT embeddings. The information is processed bidirectionally in NLP-BiLSTM, which helps to interpret the meaning of a clinical term, based on prior and succeeding context present in the narratives, which enhances the model's understanding of complex medical expressions and clinical dependencies. Optimizing techniques like adaptive learning optimization (Adam optimizer) and dropout regularization are used to reduce overfitting, which helps to boost accuracy.

Table 3. Accuracy Comparative Analysis based on Epochs

Metrics / Models	SVM ⁽⁴⁾	Random Forest ⁽³⁾	XGBoost ⁽²⁾	NLP-BiLSTM [Proposed]
Accuracy (IT-1)	77.6	79.5	81.1	92.4
Accuracy (IT-N)	74.2	76.2	79.4	89.6

3.2 Sensitivity (Recall/TPR)

The sensitivity of the proposed NLP-BiLSTM is enhanced to 91.4% which is notably high compared to existing models based on epochs and batch size tested. BiLSTM captures long-range dependencies in text, enabling it to detect symptom patterns across multiple sentences. The model recognized multiple medical terminologies with the help of ClinicalBERT integration, which reflects the robust identification of actual positive cases. Dual-context processing helps the model reduce false negatives. The reliable classification of both epileptic and non-epileptic patients is validated in all iterations across diverse clinical documentation styles. As a result, the NLP-BiLSTM achieves higher recall, ensures fewer epilepsy cases are missed in prediction, and highlights the superior diagnostic capability compared to SVM, RF, and XGBoost classifiers shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Sensitivity Comparative Analysis based on Epochs

Metrics / Models	SVM ⁽⁴⁾	Random Forest ⁽³⁾	XGBoost ⁽²⁾	NLP-BiLSTM [Proposed]
Sensitivity (IT-1)	75.4	78.8	83.4	91.4
Specificity (IT-N)	72.6	75.6	78.2	88.7

3.3 Specificity (TNR)

The specificity comparative analysis of the proposed NLP-BiLSTM model is showcased in Table 5. As the model is a carefully structured NLP pipeline, which includes Tokenization (TK) and Lemmatization (LM), it helps to break down all the clinical narratives to normal units by eliminating noise and redundant lexical variants. NER enhances specificity by isolating all the clinical narratives irrelevant to epilepsy and helps the model distinguish between overlapping symptoms. The cross-entropy loss function plays a prominent role by penalizing incorrect predictions severely when the model is confidently wrong, especially in identifying non-epileptic cases. This boosts the NLP-BiLSTM model to make event-based predictions by learning discriminative patterns specific to negative cases, which leads to more selective and reliable classification output.

Table 5. Specificity Comparative Analysis based on Epochs

Metrics / Models	SVM ⁽⁴⁾	Random Forest ⁽³⁾	XGBoost ⁽²⁾	NLP-BiLSTM [Proposed]
Specificity (IT-1)	77.4	79.8	83.4	91.6
Specificity (IT-N)	71.5	74.8	77.6	89.8

3.4 F1-Score

The comparative analysis of F1-score metric for the existing and proposed models is given in Table 6. During implementation phase and in every epoch, NLP-BiLSTM outperforms existing models by balancing precision and recall optimally. This improvement is driven by the model using deep contextual learning. The cross-entropy loss function significantly contributed to the model avoiding uncertain predictions from HER narratives. Model's generalization ability is enhanced by reducing the overfitting due to dropout regularization. As NLP-BiLSTM follows bidirectional learning from HER, precision is improved. Initial pre-processing helps the model make consistent predictions across iterations, elevating F1-score with an outstanding result of 92.4% for initial iteration and 90.2% for final iteration, which is higher than prevailing models like SVM, RF, and XGBoost.

Table 6. F1-Score Comparative Analysis based on Epochs

Metrics / Models	SVM ⁽⁴⁾	Random Forest ⁽³⁾	XGBoost ⁽²⁾	NLP-BiLSTM [Proposed]
F1-Score (IT-1)	77.3	79.4	83.6	92.4
F1-Score (IT-N)	73.4	77.6	81.2	90.2

3.5 Precision

The precision comparative analysis is demonstrated in Table 7. NLP-BiLSTM achieved high precision results of 91.4% and 88.6% during its 1st and Nth iterations, significantly higher than existing models. The proposed model has completely minimized the false positive rates when classifying the epileptic patients. In BiLSTM, the clinical records are processed forward and backward to detect deep patterns in complex texts. The phrases are completely isolated with the help of ClinicalBERT in all iterations. The continuous training of enriched feature sets is fine-tuned and optimized to retain the model's consistency and predict quality output across epochs. This resulted in a high precision value marked by a complete reduction in the misclassification of non-epileptic cases as epileptic and vice versa. The proposed NLP-BiLSTM model enhanced overall diagnostic precision during initial and final iterations.

Table 7. Precision Comparative Analysis based on Epochs

Metrics / Models	SVM ⁽⁴⁾	Random Forest ⁽³⁾	XGBoost ⁽²⁾	NLP-BiLSTM [Proposed]
Precision (IT-1)	74.4	76.3	83.4	91.4
Precision (IT-N)	70.7	75.4	81.8	88.6

3.6 AUC-ROC

The AUC-ROC analysis of the proposed NLP-BiLSTM model has significantly improved in discriminating the epileptic and non-epileptic patients across all iterations with different thresholds. The model achieved a superior AUC-ROC of 0.89, reflecting a strong prediction capability compared to SVM, RF, and XG-Boost. BiLSTM adjusts its internal states based on clinical EHR features to reduce the decision boundary confusion in all epochs. The low false positive rate of 0.11 shows the outperformance in decision making and automated diagnosis of epilepsy. By deep learning from ClinicalBERT embeddings, the proposed NLP-BiLSTM enhances the separation between closely related diagnostic features. The integration of calibrated probability outputs improved AUC-ROC and ensured optimal classification across all iterations. Cross entropy loss and Adam optimizer are employed for optimization, fine-tuning, and avoiding overfitting by the loss function, which helps to boost accurate favorable rates.

Table 8. AUC-ROC Comparative Analysis based on Epochs

Metrics / Models	SVM ⁽⁴⁾	Random Forest ⁽³⁾	XGBoost ⁽²⁾	NLP-BiLSTM [Proposed]
TPR	0.74	0.76	0.79	0.89
FPR	0.26	0.24	0.21	0.11

Fig 7. Performance Comparative Analysis Chart using Matplot

4 Conclusion

The proposed research presents a novel deep learning method with an NLP-enhanced BiLSTM network for automated and early diagnosis of epilepsy from unstructured narrative EHRs. The proposed model effectively captures the rich contextual information embedded in physician notes, diagnostic descriptions, and discharge summaries using the clinical narratives rather than structured data or EEG signal readings. NLP tokenization, lemmatization, and NER techniques are combined with ClinicalBERT to help robustly extract the epilepsy related features. The BiLSTM model is trained with cross-entropy loss and

Fig 8. AUC-ROC Analysis Chart using Matplot

optimized using the Adam optimizer with hyperparameter tuning to boost the performance. After 25 successful epochs, the superior results across the metrics are achieved with an accuracy of 92%, sensitivity of 91%, specificity of 91.6%, precision of 91%, F1-score of 92.4%, and an AUC-ROC of 0.89 compared to baseline models XG-Boost, Random Forest, and SVM. The findings demonstrate the robustness, real-world applicability, and scalability for clinical deployment. The model's ability to capture unstructured clinical text makes it a pioneer in telehealth and resource-limited settings where access to EEG diagnostics may be constrained.

Though the BiLSTM model achieved high accuracy, it depends deeply on the clarity and reliability of clinical notes. It may slow down or lack performance with poorly documented or ambiguous narratives. The model also requires substantial computational resources for multi-process training, especially when using contextual embeddings like ClinicalBERT on large-scale and real-time datasets.

5 List of Abbreviations

1. BiLSTM – Bidirectional Long-Short Term Memory
2. NER - Named Entity Recognition
3. TK - Tokenization
4. LM - Lemmatization
5. NLP – Natural Language Processing
6. RP – Reference Points
7. EEG – Electroencephalogram Signals
8. BCI – Brain Computer Interface
9. CNR – Clinical Narrative Records
10. EHR- Electronic Health Records

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References

- 1) Kuneekar P, Gupta MK, Gaur P. Detection of epileptic seizure in EEG signals using machine learning and deep learning techniques. *Journal of Engineering and Applied Science*. 2024;71:21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s44147-023-00353-y>.

- 2) Betgeri SS, Shukla M, Kumar D, Khan SB, Khan MA, Alkhalidi NA. Enhancing Seizure Detection with Hybrid XGBoost and Recurrent Neural Networks. *Neuroscience Informatics*. 2025;p. 100206. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.neuri.2025.100206>.
- 3) Zhao X, Yoshida N, Ueda T, Sugano H, Tanaka T. Epileptic seizure detection by using interpretable machine learning models. *Journal of Neural Engineering*. 2023;20(1):015002. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1741-2552/acb089>.
- 4) Atlam HF, Aderibigbe GE, Nadeem MS. Effective Epileptic Seizure Detection with Hybrid Feature Selection and SMOTE-Based Data Balancing Using SVM Classifier. *Applied Sciences*. 2025;15(9):4690. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app15094690>.
- 5) Mora S, Turrissi R, Chiarella L, et al. NLP-based tools for localization of the epileptogenic zone in patients with drug-resistant focal epilepsy. *Scientific Reports*. 2024;14:2349. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-024-51846-6>.
- 6) Leeshma K, Praveena M. Natural Language Processing and Machine Learning Based Automated Diagnosis of Epilepsy in Electronic Health Record. Ghaziabad, India. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICCS62048.2024.10830353>.
- 7) Iapascurta V, Fiodorov I. NLP Tools for Epileptic Seizure Prediction Using EEG Data: A Comparative study of three ML models. *IFMBE Proceedings (Springer)*. 2023;92:170–180. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-42782-4_19.
- 8) Liu S, Zhou Y, Yang X, Wang X, Yin J. A Robust Automatic Epilepsy Seizure Detection Algorithm Based on Interpretable Features and Machine Learning. *Electronics*. 2024;13(14):2727. <https://doi.org/10.3390/electronics13142727>.
- 9) Decker BM, Turco A, Xu J, Terman SW, Kosaraju N, Jamil A, et al. Development of a natural language processing algorithm to extract seizure types and frequencies from the electronic health record. *Seizure: European Journal of Epilepsy*. 2022;101:48–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seizure.2022.07.010>.
- 10) Nithyanandh S. Object Detection & Analysis with Deep CNN and Yolov8 in Soft Computing Frameworks. *International Journal of Soft Computing and Engineering (IJSCE)*. 2025;14(6):19–27. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijsc.E3653.14060125>.
- 11) Eguia H, Sánchez-Bocanegra CL, Vinciarelli F, Alvarez-Lopez F, Saigí-Rubió F. Clinical Decision Support and Natural Language Processing in Medicine: Systematic Literature Review. *Journal of Medical Internet Research*. 2024;26. <https://doi.org/10.2196/55315>.
- 12) Booker J, Penn J, Noor K, Dobson RJB, Fersht N, Funnell JP, et al. Utilizing Natural Language Processing to Identify Brain Tumor Patients for Clinical Trials: Development and Initial Evaluation. *World Neurosurgery*. 2025;197:123907. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wneu.2025.123907>.
- 13) Zhao W, Wang WF, Patnaik LM, Zhang BC, Weng SJ, Xiao SX, et al. Residual and bidirectional LSTM for epileptic seizure detection. *Frontiers in Computational Neuroscience*. 2024;18:1–17. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fncom.2024.1415967>.
- 14) Nithyanandh S, Jaiganesh V. Interrogation of Dynamic Node Link Failure by Utilizing Bio Inspired Techniques to Enhance Quality of Service in Wireless Sensor Networks. *Shodhganga*. 2020;p. 400513. Available from: <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/400513>.
- 15) Nazari J, Nasrabadi AM, Menhaj MB, Raiesdana S. Epilepsy seizure prediction with few-shot learning method. *Brain Informatics*. 2022;9:21. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40708-022-00170-8>.
- 16) Wang X, Wang Y, Liu D, et al. Automated recognition of epilepsy from EEG signals using a combining space–time algorithm of CNN-LSTM. *Scientific Reports*. 2023;13:14876. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-023-41537-z>.
- 17) Nithyanandh S, Omprakash S, Megala D, Karthikeyan MP. Energy Aware Adaptive Sleep Scheduling and Secured Data Transmission Protocol to enhance QoS in IoT Networks using Improved Firefly Bio-Inspired Algorithm (EAP-IFBA). *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*. 2023;16(34):2753–2766. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v16i34.1706>.
- 18) Shoeibi A, Khodatars M, Ghassemi N, Jafari M, Moridian P, Alizadehsani R, et al. Epileptic Seizures Detection Using Deep Learning Techniques: A Review. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*. 2021;18(11):5780. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph18115780>.
- 19) Eldho KJ, Nithyanandh S. Lung Cancer Detection and Severity Analysis with a 3D Deep Learning CNN Model Using CT-DICOM Clinical Dataset. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*. 2024;17(10):899–910. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v17i10.3085>.
- 20) Arularasan R, Balaji D, Garugu S, Jallepalli VR, Nithyanandh S, Singaram G. Enhancing Sign Language Recognition for Hearing-Impaired Individuals Using Deep Learning. Tiptur, India. 2024. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ICDSNS62112.2024.10690989>.
- 21) Selvam N, Joy JK. Plant Leaf Disease Detection with Multivariable Feature Selection Using Deep Learning AEN and Mask R-CNN in PLANT-DOC Data. *Biotech Research Asia*. 2024;21(4). <http://dx.doi.org/10.13005/bbra/3333>.
- 22) Devi PA, Megala D, Paviyasre N, Nithyanandh S. Robust AI Based Bio Inspired Protocol using GANs for Secure and Efficient Data Transmission in IoT to Minimize Data Loss. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*. 2024;17(35):3609–3622. <https://doi.org/10.17485/IJST/v17i35.2342>.
- 23) Johnson AEW, Bulgarelli L, Shen L, Gayles A, Shammout A, Horng S, et al. MIMIC-IV, a freely accessible electronic health record dataset. *Scientific Data*. 2023;10(1). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-022-01899-x>.
- 24) Prabhu TS, Nithyanandh S, Eldho KJ, Karthikeyan B, Vasanthi V. Securing next generation 6G wireless networks through intelligent bio-inspired routing with energy optimization for enhanced authentication. *Indian Journal of Science and Technology*. 2025;18(23):1882–1895. <https://doi.org/10.17485/ijst/v18i23.850>.
- 25) Tan S, Tang C, Ng JS, Ng C, Kovoov JG, Gupta AK, et al. Identifying epilepsy surgery candidates with natural language processing: A systematic review. *Journal of Clinical Neuroscience*. 2023;114:104–109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jocn.2023.06.010>.
- 26) Decker BM, Turco A, Xu J, Terman SW, Kosaraju N, Jamil A, et al. Development of a natural language processing algorithm to extract seizure types and frequencies from the electronic health record. *Seizure: European Journal of Epilepsy*. 2022;101:48–51. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.seizure.2022.07.010>.